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REVOLUTION OF EDUCATION PARADIGM AFTER COVID-19

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Abstract: Education systems are facing a serious challenge from the COVID-19 pandemic. In all of the world's civilized nations, education is the top development focus and metric. The worldwide COVID-19 pandemic has completely altered the educational landscape. A well-rounded and efficient educational approach is what is required in this time of crisis to develop the potential of young minds. In addition to ensuring India's general progress, it will help people obtain the skills necessary to increase their employability, productivity, health, and well-being in the coming decades. The goal of the current study is to discuss prospective paradigm shifts in the field of education.

Keywords: Covid-19, Online Class, Paradigm shift, Pedagogy

1.1 Introduction

Every element of human life was impacted by the unanticipated Covid-19 pandemic epidemic, not just in developing nations but everywhere in the world (Bacher-Hicks et al., 2020). However, education has been particularly heavily damaged. Schools, colleges, and universities have all been significantly impacted. Over 800 million students worldwide are affected, 1 in 5 cannot attend school, 1 in 4 cannot enrol in higher education classes, and 102 countries have ordered nationwide school closures while 11 have implemented localised school closures, according to the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO).

More than 200,000 coronavirus cases have been documented worldwide in more than 160 nations, causing more than 8,000 fatalities and leaving numerous States struggling with serious outbreaks. In order to flatten the curve and stop the spread of the disease, lockdown and homebound techniques have been implemented (Sintema, 2020). The COVID-19 epidemic will have a negative effect on the progress some countries made in raising the budget for education. Therefore, all governments, stakeholders, and communities must give this situation their immediate attention and take coordinated action.

Millions of youngsters miss school every day as a result of emergencies and ongoing humanitarian crises. The situation of students in nations experiencing, recovering from, or afflicted by conflict and calamity has been made worse by the COVID-19 outbreak. The Global Campaign for Education (GCE) respects the public health decision to close schools, but we think emergency plans should be in place to guarantee that children have access to education even in dire circumstances. No matter their circumstances or place of residence, GCE is convinced that every student has a right to an education. In times of crisis, education is a fundamental right for kids, teens, and adults, and it needs to be prioritised immediately away in all emergency operations.

2.1 Literature Review

According to Adnan et al [2020], COVID-19 impacted the conventional learning method of academic institutions across the world. The administrations of schools, colleges and universities opted for online lectures/classes as an alternative way to resume education. Although online learning is proving helpful in safeguarding students' and faculty's health amid COVID-19 pandemic.

Basilaiia [2020] stated that the COVID-19 crisis has led to an education crisis for which no one was prepared. School closures worldwide have affected millions of pupils the effects of which are yet to be known. 'Emergency remote teaching' as a temporary solution has been adopted in order to mitigate the effects of the pandemic on education.

The traditional classroom setting, where the teacher uses teaching aids like books and chalkboards. Education that takes place in modern classrooms that have whiteboards, projectors, or other audio-visual display devices, as well as digital boards. Online education uses communications and information technology to support learning and knowledge development from various remote locations. The learning environment is created using the internet, video/audio/text communication, and software.

Online learning is the use of any electronic device for educational purposes, and includes the delivery of content over a computer network, in the form of audio or video, interactive television, satellite broadcasts, etc (Shee & Wang, 2008). E-learning has evolved to be more networked, user-

centered, personalised, ubiquitous, and long-lasting as learning becomes more collaborative, pervasive, learner-centered, and individualised (Motiwalla,2007). There is a considerable demand for e-learning from businesses to institutions as a result of the success factors of e-learning in bridging the learning gap in a global society (Sun et al., 2008).

E-learning, in the opinion of Bouhnik (2006), has four benefits: students have the freedom to schedule their own lessons, which frees up teachers' time; students are free to express their opinions and ask questions; and students have the freedom to select the subjects and related materials they are interested in studying.

According to the literature review, teaching-learning processes are necessary for children who are enduring hardship at home without attending school in order to participate in e-assessments. However, consistent use of e-learning platforms and a thorough revision of the burden placed on studies during pandemics are essential for the effectiveness of e-assessments.

3.1 Education Through Online

E-learning resources have been essential in facilitating student learning while schools and universities have been closed due to the pandemic (Subedi et al., 2020). Schools, training centres, and higher education institutions have been forced to close in the majority of countries as a result of lockdown and social isolation measures brought on by the COVID-19 epidemic. The way educators deliver high-quality instruction—through a variety of online platforms—has undergone a paradigm shift. Despite the difficulties faced by both teachers and students, online learning, distant learning, and continuing education have emerged as a cure-all for this unprecedented worldwide pandemic. Learning would present new difficulties, it is important to never dismiss any potential for innovation in the higher education industry during these trying times. The level of online teaching and learning in the public domain has been the subject of a great deal of debate. This study gathers evidence for online teaching and learning in the Covid-19 era using secondary data (previous work). Its goal is to advance knowledge about lockdown-related online teaching and learning practices, associated difficulties, and COVID-19-induced opportunities.

Implemented more widely, instructors have embraced "Education in Emergency" through a variety of online platforms and are forced to use a system for which they are unprepared. E-learning resources have been essential in facilitating student learning while universities and schools have been closed due to the pandemic.

4.1 Online versus Offline

The disastrous Covid-19 outbreak and the installation of national lockdown in several countries have caused a transition in teaching and studying from the traditional class-based model to online learning throughout institutions worldwide. While most academics and students have favoured the old system, transitioning to online learning presented new difficulties for both groups. Whether online learning is superior to classroom-based learning is the main issue that many people are interested in exploring. Few research have made an attempt to solve this conundrum (Flores & Gago, 2020; Mariia, & Strzelecki, 2020; Wargadinata et al., 2020; Wendelboe et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2020). They demonstrate that despite the difficulties of online learning, traditional face-to-face instruction is still favoured.

Student Representative Councils (SRCs) in several institutions demanded the availability of digital learning devices (smartphones, tablets, and laptops) and internet data to all students in an effort to ensure that all students had equitable access to online learning (Kwabena & Boateng, 2020).

4.2 Online Education

Debasish Biswas [2020] stated that technology's development has fundamentally altered how education is delivered. In actuality, online learning has developed into a flexible teaching style that allows students to quickly access study materials from the comfort of their homes. Online learning also supports students in choosing their own study pace and offers a great chance for those who are unable to enroll in regular classroom settings.

Students who study online have access to an endless supply of educational resources and are helped to develop the habit of self-discipline. If the students have the required tools and access to a reliable internet connection, they can simply determine their own learning speed.

The teachers can design instructional courses, training programmes, and skill development programmes using some of the online platforms now in use, such as Microsoft Teams, Google Classroom, Canvas, and Blackboard (Petrie, 2020).

4.3 Offline Education

The conventional alternative to internet learning, offline education was the first way for students to regularly interact with their peers and teachers in person. Despite predictions that online education will eventually replace traditional classroom instruction, this is not the case.

Additionally, offline instruction gives teachers the chance to keep an eye on their students' actions and answers and intervene as needed. Therefore, whatever how sophisticated online education is, offline education will always be essential to students' overall growth.

5.1 Mode of Education in Online Classes

According to Rapanta [2020], Teachers can quickly instruct their students in virtual classrooms when it comes to online classes. As long as they have sufficient access to an internet connection, students can effortlessly access educational resources from any location. Teachers who teach online have access to a variety of online learning resources, including virtual whiteboards, conference rooms, audio and video files, animations, and live conversations with the students.

5.2 Accessibility

The ability to attend online courses from any location is one of their biggest benefits. Students can easily log in from any location to access course materials from the comfort of their own homes. Students can now easily attend lectures from the comfort of their homes thanks to apps like Zoom, Google Meet and Microsoft Team. Online learning therefore offers the clear benefit of mobility.

However, students must travel to the location of their educational institution for offline lessons. The actual classroom or lecture hall where instruction takes place is a fixed location. Some students might have to drive a long distance to go to their chosen educational facility, which could be very inconvenient.

5.3 Time Management

In the year 2020, Yuval Zolotov stated that the major obstacle for students taking online programmes is time management. Online students frequently lack a proper schedule and are distracted by several tasks. Since online classes offer the benefit of self-paced study, some students may lack a set timetable and develop the procrastinating habit. Additionally, because they must spend a lot of time signed in to their online classes, students may find other things to do online or check their social media accounts.

In offline classes, students are required to follow a rigid timetable that has been established by the instructors. Additionally, because there is synchronous learning, students will be expected to finish their assignments and projects on time.

5.4 Flexibility of Classes

The primary benefit of online education is their flexibility. It gives them the freedom to learn at their own pace without feeling any additional strain. Students can simply attend courses whenever and wherever it is convenient because they have access to recorded videos and online reading material. Additionally, it provides students more time to absorb the reading material and finish their assignments or research at their own pace.

When it comes to offline education, there is some rigidity. Since there are no easily accessible pre-recorded films or notes for the students, they must arrive at their lectures or sessions on time. As a result, students must adhere to a rigid timetable established by their educational institution.

5.5 Student-Teacher Interaction

Contrary to popular thought, there is plenty of interaction between students and teachers on the online platform. This is in contrast to the common perception that there is little to no connection between students and teachers in online education. Students can communicate with their instructors online at any time and from any place. Additionally, two-way communication is possible in online classes, which has a big impact on learning. In online classes, there may be both synchronous and asynchronous student-teacher interaction.

Since instruction is synchronous, there is face-to-face interaction even in offline classes. Active communication between students and teachers enables them to have engaging discussions and debates. Additionally, it enables students to ask questions right away and get answers quickly. To engage students, teachers are adjusting to various instructional strategies.

6.1 Conclusion

A thorough instruction manual for creating a systematic literature review has been provided in this article. Innovative and new instructional and assessment approaches must be used immediately. We now have the chance to introduce digital learning as a result of the COVID-19 epidemic. The information gap, the unfavorable environment for learning at home, equity, and academic excellence in higher education are just a few of the deficiencies that research has highlighted. Other deficiencies include the weak infrastructure for online teaching, the limited exposure of teachers to online teaching, and the lack of online teaching experience. This article assesses how the COVID-19

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epidemic has affected teaching and learning practices around the world. The difficulties and possibilities of online and continuing education during the COVID-19 epidemic are outlined, and a course of action is recommended. Future paradigm shifts in the field of education are thoroughly examined in this article.

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